

STAGES AND PROSPECTS OF DEVELOPMENT OF THE MORTGAGE MARKET OF UZBEKISTAN

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In recent years, the housing issue in Uzbekistan has been gradually developing, becoming one of the top priorities of state policy. In particular, great attention is paid to meeting the demand and needs of the population for housing through the formation and development of the mortgage market. In Uzbekistan, especially in the Khorezm region, certain successes have been achieved in this process, but there are also issues awaiting resolution. A large number of documents have been adopted for this. In particular, the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-5886 dated November 28, 2019 “On additional measures to improve mortgage lending mechanisms” , Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers No. 182 of March 25, 2020 “On approval of the Regulation on the procedure for paying subsidies to citizens for the purchase of housing” , Decrees of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-33 dated December 9, 2021 “On additional measures to provide the population with housing through mortgage loans based on market principles” and many other documents have been adopted.

In order to ensure the quality of the implementation of the adopted documents, it is necessary to increase the responsibility and accountability of the heads of state bodies.

Based on the Presidential Decrees, annual programs for the development of the mortgage market are developed. Based on these programs, new approaches are taken to meet the housing needs and demands of the population.

In accordance with the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-26 dated February 21 of this year “On additional measures for the further development of the housing and mortgage market” The main goal is to build 135 thousand apartment buildings by 2025.

It is important to expand the scale of modern housing construction and the types of mortgage products in our country, and reforms in this area will serve to further improve the living standards of the population, develop urbanization processes, and ultimately grow the economy.

In particular, over the past 5 years, multi-apartment housing with a total area of 21.7 million m² has been built, mortgage loans worth 67 trillion soums

have been allocated to assist the population in purchasing housing, and 44 trillion soums have been allocated from the state budget for these purposes.

More than 64 thousand citizens with low incomes have been paid more than 3.5 trillion soums in subsidies.

At the same time, the fact that the population has been increasing by about 800 thousand people and the number of new families by 300 thousand per year in recent years requires the intensification of work to meet the demand for housing.

Also, instead of 2-3-story houses, which make up about 40 percent of the multi-apartment housing stock in the republic, there are sufficient opportunities to build modern housing with social facilities and green spaces based on the principle of vertical growth.

Accordingly, the goal is to expand the scale of housing construction in the regions in accordance with the principles of urbanization and renovation, accelerate the construction of "New Uzbekistan" estates, increase the role of the capital market in providing mortgages with financial resources, and continue to refinance mortgage loans issued by commercial banks.

In accordance with the program for providing housing to the population through mortgage loans based on market principles in 2025, it is planned to build 135 thousand apartment houses in our republic with an area of 8.1 million m², increase the number of subsidies to cover part of the initial installments and interest payments on mortgage loans by 1.5 times and allocate 2.5 trillion soums from the State Budget for these purposes, allocate mortgage loans in the amount of 20.9 trillion soums to provide the housing and mortgage market with financial resources, and allocate 700 billion soums from the State Budget and 3.0 trillion soums from the own funds of commercial banks to provide working capital to construction organizations participating in the construction of multi-apartment housing in the "New Uzbekistan" and other areas.

It was also determined that in 2025, 2.5 trillion soums of subsidy funds will be allocated from the republican budget to 30 thousand families to cover part of the initial installment and interest payments on mortgage loans for the purchase of apartments in multi-storey buildings.

The decree stipulated that, starting from March 1, 2025, new territories for the "New Uzbekistan" estates will be selected in accordance with the principles of urbanization, taking into account the following criteria:

- the estate is located in the district (city) center or in the area close to it (up to 2 kilometers) and there is a demand for housing among the population living in this area;

- the estate is provided with engineering, communication and transport infrastructure or is close to existing infrastructure;

- at least 70 thousand people live in the area where the estate is to be created;

- the total area of the total number of apartments in the estate is at least 100 thousand m² and the construction of houses is planned to be at least 7 floors;

- at least 2 percent of the costs of building multi-apartment housing are directed to the creation of green areas around the housing;

- The Chairman of the Council of Ministers of the Republic of Karakalpakstan, the khokims of the regions and the city of Tashkent are personally responsible for ensuring that the territories selected for the creation of the “New Uzbekistan” estates comply with the criteria provided for in this paragraph.

In total, 4,920 multi-storey residential buildings with 221.9 thousand apartments were built in our republic over the past 3 years. In particular, 1,433 multi-storey residential buildings with 56.1 thousand apartments were built in 2022, 1,443 multi-storey residential buildings with 65.5 thousand apartments in 2023, and 2,044 multi-storey residential buildings with 100.3 thousand apartments in 2024. Of these, 76 multi-storey residential buildings with 3,676 apartments in 2022, 333 multi-storey residential buildings with 9,723 apartments in 2023, and 394 multi-storey residential buildings with 14,854 apartments in 2024 were built and commissioned in the “New Uzbekistan” estates.

At the same time, according to the Decree, in 2025, it is planned to build 543 houses with 28,219 apartments in the “New Uzbekistan” estates. In particular, it is planned to build 286 houses with 15,374 apartments, which are transferred from year to year, and 257 new multi-storey houses with 12,845 apartments.

The Decree provides that, starting from May 1, 2025, within the framework of the construction of the “New Uzbekistan” estates;

a) only legal entities that pay value added tax are allowed to participate in auctions for the lease of land plots for the construction of multi-apartment housing;

b) the auction offer for the lease of land plots for the construction of multi-apartment housing shall set a period of 15 days for the preparation of preliminary design documentation, 2 months for the implementation of design work and 3 months for the start of construction work, and shall also indicate the terms for the completion of construction and acceptance of the facility for use. In this case:

the land plots shall be sold within the period for the completion and acceptance of multi-apartment housing;

the land plot shall be withdrawn from the winner of the auction sale who has not fulfilled the requirements of the offer in accordance with the procedure established in Appendix 4 to the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-135 dated September 6, 2024 and shall be put up for repeated auction sale;

c) legal entities that lease a land plot for the construction of multi-apartment housing at auction sales shall be exempted from paying land tax on this land plot for 12 months from the date of lease.

In this case, if the multi-apartment housing is not built and put into operation within the specified period, the land tax for the period of using the privilege will be collected in the amount of 2 times;

g) at least 10 percent of the total area of land plots intended for the construction of commercial buildings in the “New Uzbekistan” estates will be put up for auction as a single lot together with the land plots allocated for the construction of housing.

The Ministry of Economy and Finance and the Central Bank have determined that, starting from March 1, 2025, commercial banks will provide loans to construction organizations carrying out the construction of multi-apartment housing in the “New Uzbekistan” estates to replenish their working capital at a rate no higher than 2 percentage points above the Central Bank’s base rate for a period of 24 months with a grace period of 12 months, and these loans will be gradually refinanced at the expense of funds allocated by the Ministry of Economy and Finance at the Central Bank’s base rate for a period of 24 months with a grace period of 12 months.

In general, continuing state programs implemented in our country to meet the housing needs and demands of the population, especially low-income families, and accelerating the construction of multi-storey housing based on green principles remain important elements of regulating the mortgage market.